

STFC

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	https://stfc.ukri.org/stfc/cache/file/D0D76309-252B-4EEF-A7BFAF6271B8EC11.pdf
Definition of data	Data obtained through grants to universities in particle physics, astronomy and nuclear physics, data obtained through access to beam time at STFC supported facilities, through STFC subscriptions to other organisations, and data produced as a result of past funding from STFC or its predecessor organisations, which has already been curated. All data expected to be produced from 'raw' to 'published'.
Length of data management plan	No longer than 2 pages of A4
DMP template/ requirements	How data will be managed throughout the project and retained for long-term use. Encouraged to utilise Digital Curation Centre for template/ guidance.
Required data repository	None specified, but expects use of an established repository unless good justifications for not doing so are given.
Time for data release	After initial proprietary period and within 6 months of publication.
Time for long-term storage of data	For a minimum of 10 years from end of project or indefinitely for data that would not be able to be re-measured.
Costings	Costs will be considered as part of the peer-review process.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	enquiries@stfc.ac.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

STFC Scientific data policy <https://stfc.ukri.org/stfc/cache/file/D0D76309-252B-4EEF-A7BFAF6271B8EC11.pdf>

STFC data management plan <https://stfc.ukri.org/funding/research-grants/data-management-plan/>

STFC data management review guidance <https://stfc.ukri.org/funding/research-grants/peer-review-and-assessment/data-management-review-guidance/>

Accessed: May 2018